

CONCURRENT SONIFICATION OF DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE VALUES: THE CASE OF DATABASE VALUES ABOUT STATISTICS OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Gion van den Broek

Roberto Bresin

Eindhoven University of Technology
Eindhoven, The Netherlands
g.d.v.d.broek@student.tue.nl

KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Stockholm, Sweden
roberto@kth.se

ABSTRACT

The quality of employee engagement at work is an important factor that can have effects on health, give indications on the quality of leadership, and save costs for companies. Gallup firm has defined three categories of employees that every organization in the world has: Engaged, Not engaged, Actively disengaged. Data collected with about 155000 interviews by Gallup across 155 countries around the world show that only 15% of employees worldwide are engaged in their job, 67% are not engaged, and 18% are actively disengaged. This large amount of data provides the context for reflecting on workplace conditions and engagement at work across global regions. In this paper we present a study in which we use interactive sonification strategies for representing the above three employee categories in order to explore, understand, and reflect on workplace conditions. For the sound design we applied principles of communication of emotional expression in music performance. By leveraging on the strong emotional component offered by expressive interactive sonification it was possible to create sonifications which could help participants in an experiment to identify the three different employees categories and to design the soundscape of their workplace.

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of employee engagement at work is an important factor that can have effects on health, give indications on the quality of leadership, and save costs for companies. Gallup Inc. firm conducts every year a global survey about the state of workplace in all five continents for understanding “the collective voice of the global employee” [1].

Gallup has defined three categories of employees that every organization in the world has (e.g. companies, governments):

Engaged: *Employees are highly involved in and enthusiastic about their work and workplace. They are psychological “owners”, drive performance and innovation, and move the organization forward*

Not engaged: *Employees are psychologically unattached to their work and company. Because their engagement needs are not being fully met, they are putting time — but not energy or passion — into their work*

Actively disengaged: *Employees aren’t just unhappy at work — they are resentful that their needs aren’t being met and are acting out their unhappiness. Every day, these workers potentially undermine what their engaged coworkers accomplish*

Data collected by Gallup in 2014, 2015 and 2016 across 155 countries around the world (about 1000 interviews per country) show that only 15% of employees worldwide are engaged in their job, 67% are not engaged, and 18% are actively disengaged.

From the Gallup annual survey it clearly emerges that there are large differences between the five continents and between countries in the same continent about how employee engagement at workplace varies.

This wealth of data provides the context for reflecting on workplace conditions and engagement at work across global regions. In this paper we present a study in which we use interactive sonification strategies for representing the above three employee categories in order to explore, understand, and reflect on the data in the Gallup report by using sound only. We believe that sound, as an alternative to list of numbers and histograms, adds a strong emotional component to the representation of these data and the dramatic situation of the state of workplaces they depict.

The idea of using sonification for the communication of data representing percentage values is not new and has been investigated in several previous studies, for example in the sonification of pie charts [2] and of box-plots [3].

What it is new, at our knowledge, it is the simultaneous sonification of three percentage values forming the soundscape of employee engagement at workplace in different parts of the world. In the following sections we illustrate how we designed and evaluated this sonification.

2. DESIGN PROCESS

The main idea behind the sound design presented in this section was that the sonified data should create a soundscape that resembles a work environment. Data about the state of the workplaces around the globe were provided in a survey by Gallup [1]. These data contain three parameters for each continent and for each of the 155 countries analysed: the percentage of engaged workers; the percentage of not engaged workers; the percentage of actively disengaged workers. For every parameter there should be a distinguishable sound. These three sounds will then be played simultaneously creating a soundscape with three layers that resembles a workplace. Workplaces with different values of the three percentages will be characterized by different soundscapes.

We used Pure Data¹ for implementing the sonification of the percentage of each of the three categories (engaged, not engaged, actively disengaged) as presented in the next sections. The values of the percentages for each category, provided by Gallup, can be

¹<https://puredata.info/>

set in the Pure Data patch manually by typing in the percentages in the message boxes for each category, connected to the corresponding sound.

2.1. Engaged Workers Sound

The sound used for sonifying the percentage of the engaged workers is an arpeggiator that moves upwards from the first note in the D major scale starting with D5 (587.33 Hz) to E5 (659.25 Hz), F#5 (739.99 Hz), A5 (880 Hz) and continuing looping between this four notes. This frequency range for the notes was chosen because they fall in the range of frequencies that listeners associate more often to happy music performances [4]. The arpeggiator has a steady rhythm, as most people associate that to positive and energetic emotions [5, 6]. The rhythm of the arpeggiator depends on the value of the percentage of the data. The formula for this is as follows:

$$Tempo = Value \times 3.6 \quad (1)$$

Where:

Tempo is the rhythm of the arpeggiator in BPM, with a limit at 140 BPM

Value is the input data in percentages

The timbre is a simple sinewave oscillator with a short attack and decay, making it sound like a pluck. When the percentage of engaged workers increases, the tempo (beats per minute) and the amplitude will also increase, thus making the sound playing faster and louder and vice versa. Because no workplace in the Gallup data used had a percentage of engaged workers higher than 31, the parameter changing the sound was limited to create more variety at lower percentages and to prevent that the sound would be too loud or too fast at percentages greater than 31.

Example of this sound design for engaged workers at 31% is the sound Q11.wav².

2.2. Not Engaged Workers Sound

The sound used for sonifying the percentage of the not engaged workers is build up out of three sinewave oscillators, that start out playing the same frequency, continuously, creating a droning pad-like sound. This pad sound adds to the passive characteristic of the sound. The note is B1 (61.74 Hz) because this note is in the range of frequencies that most people associate to low active and/or negative emotions in musical expression, as found in a previous study on the control of real-time synthesis of emotional expression [4] and implemented in expressive performance tools (e.g. [7, 8]). When the percentage of not engaged workers gets a different value, two of the oscillators will play with a frequency that changes, while the other one will keep playing B1. This means that when the percentage increases, the pad will get a different harmony, with frequencies that are more apart, thus creating a thicker and more atonal sound, making it more present and uneasy. The depth between the frequencies is low and it has a slow rate, creating a humming, chorus like effect to the sound when percentages increase. Next to this the pad has a chorus effect that increases its depth and rate, adding a bit of boisterousness to the sound, when the percentage gets higher. The amplitude of the pad also changes according to the percentage. This sound had no limitations as the domain of the data was large enough to clearly hear differences even above the maximum values in this data set (74%).

²Q11.wav <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7010600>

Example of this sound design for not engaged workers at 74% is the sound Q14.wav³.

2.3. Actively Disengaged Workers Sound

The sound used for sonifying the percentage of actively disengaged workers is made with two arpeggiators, one panned to the left channel and the other to the right, to create more space in the mix as well as giving the sound more chaotic characteristics. When the percentage of the actively disengaged workers increases, both arpeggiators get panned more towards the center, making them more apparent in the soundscape. The arpeggiators are implemented with a ring modulation of two sawtooth generators and a sinewave oscillator, creating a distorted bass pluck sound, the low noisy sound creates an irritating effect. The lowest frequency from the sideband plays a random generated note in the range between C2 (65.41 Hz) and A2 (110.00 Hz), as frequencies below C3 has been found to be associated to scary music performances [4]. One of the other sidebands play the same frequency multiplied by 1.0001 and the other one, one octave higher. Both arpeggiators have a different random arrhythmic timing, adding to the chaotic characteristic which tempo increases when the percentage increases. The amplitude also increases as the percentage increases and vice versa. The maximum value of the data for actively disengaged workers is 24%, so the parameter changing the sound was limited to create more variety in the lower percentages and to prevent that the sound would become too loud or too fast at percentages greater than 24.

Example of this sound design for actively disengaged workers at 22% is the sound Q12.wav⁴.

3. METHOD

3.1. Participants

15 anonymous people participated in the experiment (7 F, 8 M). The average age was 29 years, ranging from 19 to 52 years. The nationalities were quite diverse, with mostly European and Asian people, but also some from Africa and South America. Most participants were students, engineers or workers in the service sector. Most participants did not have musical experience or just a little. Only one of them stated they had professional experience.

3.2. Stimuli

Sound stimuli were produced following the design strategies presented above (see Section 2)⁵. In the first part of the experiment participants had to answer questions about the sound stimuli. In the second part they were asked to create sounds themselves by using a MIDI controller (see Figure 1).

3.3. Procedure

The experiment was conducted in the lobby of the cinema Lab-1 in Eindhoven. First the participants had to read, complete and

³Q14.wav <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7010600>

⁴Q12.wav <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7010600>

⁵All stimuli can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7010600>

Figure 1: *Experiment setup in the lobby of Cinema Lab-1. In front of the participant is the laptop with the Pure Data interface (see Figure 2). A print-out of the Gallup graphs used in the experiment (see Figure 3) is placed on the keyboard of the laptop. In front of the laptop is the MIDI controller for controlling the sonification. On the left are the headphones used to listen to the sounds. On the right are the explanation sheets, in both dutch and english, as well as the mouse to interact with the interface and a pencil used to fill in the printed question sheets.*

sign a printed consent form. After that they could take place behind a laptop and read written instructions, in which the three categories of employee engagement were explained. When they finished reading the instructions, participants put on the headphones, AKG K371, and were instructed to start listening to the sound stimuli by clicking on the corresponding button in the interface with their mouse. The sound stimuli were organized in four different groups associated to four different questions, see Figure 2.

Participants were provided with a printed questionnaire with a set of four questions each associated to each of the sound stimuli: after each sound they had to answer to one specific question (see Section 3.4).

Before starting to listen to the set of sounds associated to the third question, participants were presented with a graphical representation of data relative to employee engagement made by Gallup, see Figure 3.

At the fourth question, participants had to make a sound representing a part of the world which they could choose from Figure 3. By turning three knobs on the controller, see Figure 1, they could set the sound of the different parameters. To prevent participants from setting the knobs to the values they see on Figure 3 the scale of each knob displayed on the screen was multiplied by a different number, so participants had to listen to create a representing sound, and not related to the number on the screen.

Overall, participants took on average 20 minutes to complete the experiment. For some participants it took a longer or shorter time, this was mostly depending on how much time they spend on controlling the sounds themselves at question four.

3.4. Questions

The first part of the questionnaire were some demographic questions, as discussed in section 3.1.

The second part of the questionnaire were the questions about the sounds. The first three questions were identification tasks. For the first question (Q1), the participants listened to a sound and after that they had to choose to which group, engaged, not engaged or actively disengaged, they thought the sound belongs to. For the second question (Q2), participants had to listen to a soundscape and after that choose which group they thought was the most present in the soundscape of the workplace. For the third question (Q3), after the participants examined the Gallup graphs, see Figure 3, they listened to a soundscape and then had to choose one of the countries from the graph they thought the soundscape represented.

The fourth question (Q4) consisted of two production tasks: participants were asked (1) to compose a soundscape for the workplace of two particular parts of the world shown on the graphs (Latin America and Eastern Europe, see Figure 3) and (2) to compose a soundscape that represented the state of their own workplace.

The last part of the questionnaire consisted of three reflective questions about their experience of the sounds and composing the sounds and their view on data sonification. Next to this, there was room for extra comments by the participants.

The Pure Data interface used for these questions is shown in Figure 2.

4. RESULTS

For the analysis of results presented in this section, the 15 participants were divided into three categories depending on the sector of their work: Engineers, Service personnel, Students. There were in total 4 engineers, 7 service workers, and 4 students.

4.1. Question 1

For Question 1, see Section 3.4, it was chosen to only show the graphs of the sounds that were clearly identified by the participants. We do not present results that were not significant.

The first sound, see Figure 4, was mostly identified as a sound belonging to the Engaged group. None of the participants identified it as a sound belonging to the Actively Disengaged group. All of the participants working as Students recognized the sound as Engaged.

The second sound, see Figure 5, was mostly identified as the sound belonging to the Actively Disengaged group. Some participants identified it as a sound belonging to the Not Engaged group. None of the participants belonging to the Student working category classified it as a sound representing Actively Disengaged workers. All of the participants belonging to the Engineer category identified the sound as representing Actively Disengaged workers.

The fourth sound, see Figure 6, was mostly classified as a sound belonging to the Not Engaged group. Some of the participants associated it to the Actively Disengaged group. None of the participants in the Student category recognized the sound as Not Engaged. All of the participants working as engineers recognized the sound as representing Not Engaged workers.

Figure 2: Experiment interface with buttons for playing the sounds for questions Q1–Q3 and for showing values for question Q4 (values were presented on a different scale for feedback purpose only).

Figure 3: Gallup data visuals that were used in the experiment.

4.2. Question 2

For Question 2, see Section 3.4, it was chosen to include the graphs of the answers for all the soundscapes, since they show clear re-

sults.

Most of the participants recognized that Not Engaged workers is the largest represented group in the first soundscape, see Figure 7. Some participants, perceived that the group of Engaged workers was the largest in the workplace this soundscape represents. Almost all participants working in the Service sector recognized that the Not Engaged group was the most represented in this workplace.

Most of the participants recognized that Engaged workers are the most represented in the second soundscape, see Figure 8. All

Number of Answers to Question 1 Sound 1

Figure 4: Number of answers for the sound stimulus representing 31% engaged employees (sound Q11.wav).

Figure 5: Number of answers for the sound stimulus representing 22% actively disengaged employees (sound Q12.wav).

Figure 7: Number of answers for the most represented employee group in a soundscape portraying 15% Engaged, 70% Not Engaged and 15% Actively Disengaged employees (sound Q21.wav).

Figure 6: Number of answers for the sound stimulus representing 74% not engaged employees (sound Q14.wav).

participants working as students and almost all participants working in the service sector recognized that the Engaged group was the most represented in this soundscape.

Most of the participants also recognized that the group of workers that are Actively Disengaged are represented with a larger percentage in the third soundscape, see Figure 9. All participants working as engineers recognized that the Actively Disengaged group was the most represented in this workplace.

4.3. Question 3

For Question 3, see Section 3.4, it was chosen to only show the graphs of the soundscapes that were clearly recognized by the participants and thus created a clear graph to show.

The first soundscape, see Figure 10, was recognized by most participants as representing the workplace of the United States and

Figure 8: Number of answers for the most represented employee group in a soundscape portraying 50% Engaged, 35% Not Engaged and 15% Actively Disengaged employees (sound Q22.wav).

Canada. Some participants recognized it as representing the workplace of Latin America. The answers of the participants were divided over seven different parts of the world, out of eleven available options.

The second soundscape, see Figure 11, was not recognized by most participants as representing a specific workplace. Participant mostly recognized it as either East Asia, Middle East/North Africa or Western Europe. The answers of the participants were divided over seven different parts of the world, out of eleven available options.

The fifth soundscape, see Figure 12, was recognized by most participants as representing the workplace of Latin America. Some participants recognized it as representing the workplace of the United

Figure 9: Number of answers for the most represented employee group in a soundscape portraying 15% Engaged, 35% Not Engaged and 50% Actively Disengaged (sound Q23.wav).

States and Canada. The answers of the participants were divided over six different parts of the world, among eleven available options.

Figure 10: Number of answers for the soundscape representing the state of the workplace of United States and Canada characterized by 31% Engaged, 52% Not Engaged and 17% Actively Disengaged (sound Q31.wav).

4.4. Question 4

The outcome of the first task in Question 4 (see Section 3.4) shows that most participants set the percentage value of engaged workers in Latin America workplaces to an average value close to that provided by Gallup Data (27%), while some of the participants selected a lower value, around 15% (see Figure 13). Most of the

Figure 11: Number of answers for the soundscape representing the state of the workplace of East Asia characterized by 6% Engaged, 74% Not Engaged and 20% Actively Disengaged (sound Q32.wav).

participants set the value of the Not Engaged group around 15%, much lower than the value found in the Gallup data. Some participants set a value of the Not Engaged group close to the value provided by Gallup (59%). Almost all participants selected a value of the Actively Disengaged group very close to the value reported in the Gallup survey (14%).

Results of the second task, i.e. to create the soundscape of the Eastern European workplace, show that the most participants selected an average value of the Engaged group, close to that provided by Gallup Data, 15% (see Figure 14). Most of the participants set the value of the Not Engaged group, close to value reported by Gallup (69%). Only a few participants selected a lower value for the Not Engaged group, around 25%. Almost all participants selected a value of the Actively Disengaged group close to that provided by Gallup (16%).

In the third task participants were asked to design the sound of own workplace. Results show that most of the participants selected a value for the Engaged group close to 15% (see Figure 15). Almost none of the participants working in the service area gave their workplace an engaged value higher than 15%, even one of them giving it the value of 0%. Two clusters of values were found for the value of the Not Engaged group: one group of participants selected a value around 20% and another group a value in the range 60%–80%. Almost all participants selected a value for the Actively Disengaged group below 20%.

5. DISCUSSION

Results show that participants could easily identify the sonification of engaged employees (see Figure 4) as well as of the actively disengaged and not engaged ones (see Figures 5 and 6). We believe that this was facilitated by the design of sonification based on principles of communication of emotional expression in music: we associated engagement to positive emotions and actively disengaged to negative emotions. Engagement was sonified applying

Figure 12: Number of answers for the soundscape representing the state of the workplace of Latin America characterized by 27% Engaged, 59% Not Engaged and 14% Actively Disengaged (sound Q35.wav).

Figure 14: Question 4, soundscape 2; Percentages participants assigned to different groups of employees when creating their own representation of the soundscape of the state of the workplace of Eastern Europe. The red dots represent the actual values provided by the Gallup data, corresponding to 15% Engaged, 69% Not Engaged and 16% Actively Disengaged.

Figure 13: Question 4, soundscape 1; Percentages participants assigned to different groups of workers when creating their own representation of the soundscape of the state of the workplace of Latin America. The red dots represent the actual values provided by the Gallup data, corresponding to 27% Engaged, 59% Not Engaged and 14% Actively Disengaged.

Figure 15: Question 4, soundscape 3; Percentages assigned by participants from different occupation classes to the three different work engagement groups when adjusting the sonification for creating the soundscape of own workplace.

acoustic cues values typical of positive emotions, while the sound qualities for actively disengaged employees were based on results from previous studies on the communication of negative emotions. Similarly, when we asked to listen to soundscapes made by concurrent percentages representing the three groups of employees, participants were able to identify the group represented by the largest percentage in each of three different soundscapes (see Figures 7, 8 and 9).

When asked to compose the soundscape for the own workplace, participants from all three occupation categories choose low percentages for Actively Disengaged, with Students selecting on

average the lowest percentage. Students were in general more positive in selecting the soundscape of their workplace, selecting a higher percentage for the Engaged category and lower for Not Engaged (see Figure 15). This could reflect the fact that students have less experience of “negative” working places and have in general a more positive attitude to job and working environments.

It seems like it was easier for participants to hear differences in the engaged workers sound than the other sounds. When identifying sounds and soundscapes there was less confusion about what it was when there was a high percentage of engaged workers sound involved compared to when the percentage of the not engaged or actively disengaged groups was higher: compare for example the answers relative to sound Q21.wav and sound Q22.wav in Question 2, see Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. This clearly shows

participants in general recognized the highly engaged groups better than highly disengaged groups. Similar results were found when participants were asked to associate soundscapes of work engagement to different countries: a higher number of participants identified US/Canada (Figure 10) compared to the number of participants who identified East Asia (Figure 11), even though East Asia has a very high percentage of actively disengaged and not engaged workers.

We observed that participants seemed to understand the data better after they had been manipulating and controlling the soundscapes themselves. Several participants stated that at first they found it hard to understand the sonification of the data and to hear clear differences, however after controlling the sounds they understood the parameters better and they felt more confident about hearing the differences. This is reflected in the following quotes taken from answers by participants to the reflective question about being able to control the sounds: “*Interesting, gave me more of a feeling for the meaning of the soundscapes.*” and “*Pretty fun to experiment with and gained better understanding of how sound signifies behaviour.*”.

Furthermore, when participants were asked to reflect about their ideas about data sonification, they overall thought it added emotional value and helped creating a better connection to the data. However, they also stated that using only sounds might be too subjective and not as precise as using data visualisations. This can also be noted in the following quotes taken from answers by participants: “*I feel like it would instil a sense of empathy with the points you want to send across, but personal experience might prove difficult in standardizing the responses and data. In a sense, it could help explaining concepts, so long people got a common reference point.*” and “*I see it as a new way to present data in an interesting and engaging way that would otherwise be boring or very abstract.*”.

6. FUTURE WORK

In the future we conduct further user testing with different orders of the tasks and also with an extended set of data from the Gallup survey. We will also test to what extend and precision participants can identify different percentage values of the three different groups of workers. Furthermore, we will test if the sonification strategy presented in this work can be applied to other data sets, for example climate change data, not only consisting in lists of percentage numbers but also characterized by social and emotional values.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research presented in this paper has been funded by the NAVET center for Research in Art, Technology and Design at KTH Royal Institute of Technology and by a grant to Roberto Bresin by the Swedish Research Council (Grant 2017-03979). We are grateful to documentary director Erik Gandini for introducing the Gallup report to us and for fruitful discussions about its data and how they could be displayed in different ways. We thank the anonymous participants to the experiment presented in this paper. In addition to this we would like to thank Cinema Lab-1 in Eindhoven for providing us with a place in their lobby to conduct the experiment. This work was made possible through an internship, presented by Eindhoven University of Technology, at the Sound

and Music Computing research group at KTH Royal Institute of Technology, facilitated by Sonja Monica Berlijn (KTH).

8. REFERENCES

- [1] Gallup Inc., *State of the global workplace*, Gallup Press, New York, 2017.
- [2] Keith Michael Franklin and Jonathan C Roberts, “Pie chart sonification,” in *Proceedings on Seventh International Conference on Information Visualization, 2003. IV 2003*. IEEE, 2003, pp. 4–9.
- [3] Sam Ferguson, William L. Martens, and Densil Cabrera, “Statistical sonification for exploratory data analysis,” in *The Sonification Handbook*, Thomas Hermann, Andy Hunt, and John G. Neuhoff, Eds., pp. 175–196. Logos Publishing House, Berlin, Germany, 2011.
- [4] Roberto Bresin and Anders Friberg, “Emotion rendering in music: range and characteristic values of seven musical variables,” *Cortex*, vol. 47, no. 9, pp. 1068–1081, 2011.
- [5] Alf Gabrielsson and Erik Lindström, “The role of structure in the musical expression of emotions,” in *Handbook of music and emotion: Theory, research, applications*, John Sloboda Patrik N. Juslin, Ed., pp. 367–44. Oxford University Press, 2010.
- [6] Patrik N Juslin and Renee Timmers, “Expression and communication of emotion in music performance,” in *Handbook of music and emotion: Theory, research, applications*, John Sloboda Patrik N. Juslin, Ed., pp. 452–489. Oxford University Press, 2010.
- [7] Anders Friberg, “pdm: an expressive sequencer with real-time control of the kth music-performance rules,” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 37–48, 2006.
- [8] R Michael Winters, Ian Hattwick, and Marcelo M Wanderley, “Emotional data in music performance: Two audio environments for the emotional imaging composer,” in *The 3rd International Conference on Music & Emotion, Jyväskylä, Finland, June 11-15, 2013*. University of Jyväskylä, Department of Music, 2013.